

Piezoelectric Materials and Applications: A Review

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Abstract

Piezoelectric materials are materials that can convert mechanical stress into electric charge, or vice versa. They have a unique crystal structure that allows them to exhibit this effect. Piezoelectric materials have wide applications in energy conversion, sensors, drives, and frequency control. In this review, we will introduce the basic principles and properties of piezoelectric materials, and discuss the different types and categories of piezoelectric materials based on their composition, structure, and performance. We will also highlight some of the current and emerging applications of piezoelectric materials in various fields and industries.

Introduction

Piezoelectricity is a phenomenon that occurs in certain materials when they are subjected to mechanical stress or strain. The word piezoelectricity comes from the Greek word piezein, which means to squeeze or press. When a piezoelectric material is deformed by an external force, it generates an electric charge on its surface. Conversely, when a piezoelectric material is exposed to an electric field, it undergoes a mechanical deformation. This bidirectional effect is known as the direct and inverse piezoelectric effect, respectively.

The piezoelectric effect was first discovered by Jacques and Pierre Curie in 1880, when they observed that quartz crystals produced electric charges when compressed or bent. Since then, many other materials have been found to exhibit piezoelectricity, such as ceramics, crystals, polymers, and thin films. Piezoelectric materials have unique properties that make them useful for various applications in energy conversion, sensors, drives, and frequency control. For example, piezoelectric materials can be used to generate electric power from mechanical vibrations or motions, such as human footsteps or ocean waves. They can also be used to measure force, pressure, acceleration, or displacement by converting them into electric signals. Moreover, piezoelectric materials can be used to create precise movements or vibrations by applying electric signals to them. This can be useful for applications such as ultrasound imaging, inkjet printing, or microelectromechanical systems (MEMS).

The performance of piezoelectric materials depends on several factors, such as their composition, structure, processing conditions, and operating conditions. Different types of piezoelectric materials have different advantages and disadvantages in terms of their piezoelectric coefficients, dielectric constants, electromechanical coupling factors, dielectric losses, mechanical strength, temperature stability, cost, toxicity, and environmental impact. Therefore, it is important to understand the characteristics and properties of different types of piezoelectric materials and select the most suitable ones for specific applications.

In this review, we will provide an overview of the basic principles and properties of piezoelectric materials. We will also discuss the different types and categories of piezoelectric materials based on their composition, structure, and performance. Furthermore, we will highlight some of the current and emerging applications of piezoelectric materials in various fields and industries.

Basic Principles and Properties of Piezoelectric Materials

Crystal Structure and Symmetry

The origin of the piezoelectric effect lies in the crystal structure and symmetry of the material. A crystal is a solid material whose atoms or molecules are arranged in a regular and repeating pattern called a lattice. The lattice can be described by three vectors called lattice constants (a, b, c) and three angles called lattice angles (α, β, γ). The smallest unit of the lattice that can represent the whole crystal is called a unit cell.

The symmetry of a crystal is the property that describes how the crystal looks the same from different directions or positions. There are 32 possible ways to arrange a unit cell with different symmetry elements, such as rotation axes, mirror planes,

inversion centers, or glide planes. These 32 ways are called point groups or crystal classes.

However, not all point groups can exhibit piezoelectricity. Only 21 out of 32 point groups are non-centrosymmetric (meaning they do not have an inversion center), which is a necessary condition for piezoelectricity. These 21 point groups are further divided into two categories: polar (meaning they have a permanent electric dipole moment) and non-polar (meaning they do not have a permanent electric dipole moment). Only 20 out of 21 non-centrosymmetric point groups are non-polar (meaning they do not have a polar axis), which is another necessary condition for piezoelectricity. These 20 point groups are called piezoelectric point groups.

A material that belongs to one of these 20 point groups has a unique crystal structure that allows it to exhibit the direct and inverse piezoelectric effect. When a mechanical stress is applied to the material, the atoms or molecules in the unit cell are displaced from their equilibrium positions, creating an electric dipole moment. The electric dipole moments of all the unit cells add up to produce an electric charge on the surface of the material. Conversely, when an electric field is applied to the material, the electric field interacts with the electric dipole moments of the unit cells, causing them to rotate or align with the field. This results in a mechanical deformation of the material.

Piezoelectric Coefficients and Matrices

The relationship between the mechanical stress and the electric charge, or between the electric field and the mechanical strain, can be quantified by a set of constants called piezoelectric coefficients. These coefficients describe how much electric charge is generated per unit of mechanical stress, or how much mechanical strain is induced per unit of electric field.

There are two types of piezoelectric coefficients: direct piezoelectric coefficients (d) and converse piezoelectric coefficients (g). The direct piezoelectric coefficients relate the electric charge density (p) to the mechanical stress (σ), while the converse piezoelectric coefficients relate the mechanical strain (ϵ) to the electric field (E). The general equations for these relationships are:

$$p = d\sigma + \epsilon E$$

$$\epsilon = gE + s\sigma$$

where ϵ is the permittivity matrix and s is the compliance matrix of the material.

The piezoelectric coefficients are usually expressed in matrix form, where each element represents a specific combination of directions for the stress, strain, charge, or field. For example, d_{31} represents the charge density generated on the 3rd direction (usually z-axis) when a stress is applied on the 1st direction (usually x-axis), while g_{15} represents the strain induced on the 1st direction when an electric field is applied on the 5th direction (usually y-axis).

The number and value of the piezoelectric coefficients depend on the symmetry of the material. For example, a material that belongs to a cubic point group has no piezoelectric coefficients, while a material that belongs to a hexagonal point group has three independent piezoelectric coefficients: d_{31} , d_{33} , and d_{15} . The higher the symmetry of the material, the lower the number and value of the piezoelectric coefficients.

Electromechanical Coupling Factor and Quality Factor

The performance of a piezoelectric material can also be characterized by two other parameters: electromechanical coupling factor (k) and quality factor (Q). These parameters describe how efficiently and effectively a piezoelectric material can convert mechanical energy into electrical energy, or vice versa.

The electromechanical coupling factor is a dimensionless parameter that measures how much energy is transferred between the mechanical and electrical domains in a piezoelectric material. It is defined as:

$$k = \sqrt{P_m/P_e}$$

where P_m is the mechanical power input or output, and P_e is the electrical power input or output.

The electromechanical coupling factor can range from 0 to 1, where 0 means no energy conversion and 1 means perfect energy conversion. A higher electromechanical coupling factor means a higher efficiency of energy conversion. The electromechanical coupling factor depends on several factors, such as the mode of vibration, the shape and size of the material, and the boundary conditions.

The quality factor is a dimensionless parameter that measures how much energy is dissipated or lost in a piezoelectric material due to various mechanisms, such as heat generation, friction, or leakage. It is defined as:

$$Q = 2\pi(E_s/E_d)$$

where E_s is the stored energy in one cycle of vibration, and E_d is the dissipated energy in one cycle of vibration.

The quality factor can range from 0 to infinity, where 0 means all energy is dissipated and infinity means no energy is dissipated. A higher quality factor means a lower energy loss. The quality factor depends on several factors, such as the frequency of vibration, the temperature of operation, and the impurities or defects in the material.

Types and Categories of Piezoelectric Materials

Lead-Based Ceramics

Lead-based ceramics are one of the most widely used types of piezoelectric materials due to their high piezoelectric coefficients and electromechanical coupling factors. They are composed of lead oxide (PbO) mixed with other metal oxides, such as zirconium oxide (ZrO₂) and titanium oxide (TiO₂). The most common lead-based ceramic is lead zirconate titanate (PZT), which has a general formula of Pb(Zr_xTi_{1-x})O₃. PZT can have different compositions depending on the ratio of zirconium to titanium (x), which affects its crystal structure and properties.

PZT can exist in three different crystal phases: rhombohedral, tetragonal, and cubic.

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